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Construction readiness of combined CCT demonstrator

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ABSTRACT

The report presents the construction readiness of the combined function CCT demonstrator. The document summarizes the components and the procedures that should be done to productively start and sustain magnet construction operations.

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Executive summary

The construction readiness of the combined CCT demonstrator based on a rope of 6 twisted NbTi strands around one copper core strand has been presented.

The document summarizes the assembly process of the demonstrator magnet with detailed 3D illustrations, and listing the main components (conductor, formers, envelope tube, end plates, and splice box) and the main procedures (winding, impregnation and mechanical assembly). The conductor is a rope (6 NbTi strands+1 copper core) with a double braid of polyester, fully characterized in terms of critical current, high voltage and splice measurements, and ready for the final production and delivery to CIEMAT (Madrid, Spain).

The former material is aluminium-bronze, chosen due to its low electrical conductivity and favourable manufacturing properties, allowing a minimum rib thickness of 0.4 mm. The outermost envelope tube of the magnet system provides mechanical support, serves as a container for wax impregnation, and is made of aluminum-bronze, while glass-fiber reinforced PEEK end plates secure and lock the tubes, with cables guided axially to a splice box for impregnation.

The report describes the winding tests and the improvements for superconducting ropes, including the need for rounded groove edges, temporary clamps, and increased insulation for successful winding in the final magnet formers. The use of wax impregnation is considered, highlighting its effectiveness in preventing quenches and describing the impregnation process within the magnet itself, aided by a polyester braid to prevent voids.

The assembly procedure involves winding two layers of 2x7 ropes on inner and outer formers, testing insulation, adding support for layer transition, installing the envelope tube, end plates, and splice box, making rope joints and voltage taps, and concluding with wax impregnation and cleanup.

Finally, the readiness table provides an overview of the construction status, indicating that the conductor and end plates are ready for construction, with some components like the envelope tube and splice box being in a medium readiness state, while winding and impregnation are generally prepared, and assembly readiness is medium with the inter-layers and second layer surfaces to be defined.

1. Introduction

Within the European project I.FAST, the work package 8, Innovative superconducting magnets, has the main objective to advance HTS (High-Temperature Superconductor) technology with CCT (Canted-Cosine Theta) layout, in a collaborative way between scientific institutes and industry. To this end, the final goal is to manufacture an HTS CCT demonstrator of about 4 T. However, this demonstrator will be preceded by a simpler magnet in LTS (Low-Temperature Superconductor) to develop competencies and expertise [1].

The combined function CCT allows exploring the new and promising technology of combined function magnets crucial for applications in small accelerator systems for cancer therapy and research activities. The main feature of the demonstrator is that superimposed to the main dipole field of 4-5 T there will be a quadrupolar component of 5-10 T/m which will yield about 0.5-1 T additional peak field [2].

The task 8.1 has the aim to coordinate and review the activities concerning the demonstrator magnet, and to verify the status and the progress done.

This document presents the construction readiness of the combined CCT demonstrator based on NbTi, following the conceptual design report presented in the deliverable D8.2 [2]. Starting from the final assembly of the magnet, the document lists all the procedural steps to implement, highlighting all the components and procedures necessary for finalizing the construction of the magnet. The review report shows also the status of advancement and eventually the missing part or steps to be established or completed.

2. Main parameters of the Demonstrator

The following section presents the tables with the final parameters of the combined function CCT magnet. Table 1 shows the main parameters, while Table 2 collects the parameters resulting from the electromagnetic design, reporting the initial and the final design values.

Table 1. Main parameters of the combined function CCT magnet.

Parameters	Value	Units
Magnet	LTS CCT	-
Geometry	Straight	-
Field type	Combined	-
Main field	4	T
Secondary field	5	T/m
Bore diameter	80	mm
Magnetic length	0.8	m
Physical length	1	m
Working temperature	4.7 (test at 4.2)	K
dB/dt	0.4	T/s
Margin on load line (static)	25	%

Table 2. Main parameters from the initial and final electromagnetic design.

Parameters	Initial design	Final design	Units
Rope diameter	2.85	3.15	mm
Number of ropes in a groove	2 x 7	2 x 7	-
Groove size	5.7 x 19.95	6.5 x 22.3	mm
Spar thickness	6	4.2 (inner), 6 (outer)	mm
Minimum rib thickness	0.4	0.4	mm
Magnet current	1500	1540	A
Pitch	12.61	14.57	mm
# of turns	54	50	-
Total rope length	862	844	m

3. Demonstrator assembly, components and procedures

3.1 ASSEMBLY OF THE MAGNET

The magnet is based on the following components: conductor, formers, envelope tube, end plates, splice box, layer jump clamps and others.

Figure 1 shows the winding/assembly process of the magnet. The inner former (1) is wound first, starting from the current lead end of the magnet (not visible in the picture). When the layer-jump end is reached, the contour of the footprints of the two-layer jump clamps (3,4), one of the contour edges being indicated by the letter (e), is covered by a self-adhesive kapton tape (2) on the surface of the inner former to provide high-voltage clearance between the inner former (1) and outer former (6). The first layer jump clamp (3) is mounted to the former, which clamps down the last turn of the winding on one hand, and constitutes one side of the cable channel in the transitioning section of the cable. The second layer jump clamp (4) is then mounted, which closes this channel and fully constrains the transitioning section of the cables. The layer jump clamps are made from 3D-printed Ultem or PEEK and their fixing bolts (not numbered in the figure) must have axial venting holes to allow the evacuation of the corresponding blind holes in the inner former. Two layers of a glass fiber tape are then wrapped tightly around the former (not shown), including the two-layer jump clamps. These serve as spacers on one hand to ensure a transfer channel for liquid wax in direct connection to the volume within the grooves, and as retainers of wax during freeze-out to provide a better mechanical consistency. Two layers of 0.1 mm thick kapton sheets (5) are wrapped around the fiber glass layers with non-overlapping slits to provide electrical insulation between the formers. The outer former (6) is then slid onto the winding. When its end reaches the layer jump feature, the glass fiber layers need to be gently pushed down on one side of the layer jump clamps [marked by (2) in Fig. 2] because this side could not be made tangential to the cylindrical surface. The other side [marked by (1) in Fig. 2] of the layer jump clamps could be made tangential and does not cause any difficulty. The winding then continues on the outer former, which is wrapped by a glass fiber tape and 2 layers of kapton foil as well. The envelope tube [item (7) in Fig. 1] is then installed, followed by the closing end-disks (8). The one on the layer jump end is sealed to the inner former by a rubber O-ring (9) to constitute the impregnation volume. Sealing to the envelope tube will be done by extra auxiliary components. No sealing is needed between the end disk and the tubes at the other end of the magnet (current lead end) since this will be included in the wax reservoir (see later).

3.2 LIST OF COMPONENTS

3.2.1 Conductor

The conductor is based on a rope 6+1 (6 NbTi strands twisted around one copper core strand) with a double braid of polyester (coverage factor of 99%), as shown in Fig. 3. The NbTi strand a low AC losses one produced for the DISCORAP project (INFN)[3], fully characterized as reported in [4]. The cabling of the rope has been made by Texcavi srl (Inzago, Italy), and the critical current measurements have qualified the industrial procedure (Figs. 3 and 4). The double braid of polyester has been fully qualified from the insulation point of view (1 kV of voltage insulation without filler, Fig. 5).

Figure 3: Rope 6+1 representation and picture of the final cable and magnet groove section.

Figure 4: Critical current measurements of rope (blue), and of the single virgin NbTi strand (red circles).

Figure 5: Voltage insulation test in a flat test piece. Having variable channel widths, this was at the same time used to evaluate the required channel dimensions. The HP-6688B has been used as a digital insulation tester.

The CCT magnet needs 13 splices to connect the 2x7 ropes (running forward on the inner former and returning on the outer former) in series. Therefore, the experimental characterization of the splicing is crucial to determine the amount of the heat load and if there is a risk of quench.

The INFN team of Milan prepared a test in liquid helium to determine the rope splice resistance in different configurations. First, an analysis of splice resistance as a function of the splice length has been done. This involved measuring the splice resistance both with and without soldering, specifically employing Sn96.5Ag3Cu0.5 for soldering. The combination of crimping and soldering achieved the lowest resistance and provides enhanced thermal and mechanical stability. However, a drawback was identified — lower resistance leading to loop currents during current ramps. Conversely, a not-stabilized splice achieved solely through crimping has been examined, offering the advantage of lower loop currents but at the expense of reduced thermal stability. Additionally, a comparative analysis between 'praying hands' and 'shaking hands' junctions has been worked out, exploring their respective characteristics and implications (Fig. 6).

The results of the test are the following:

1. The resistance of the 'praying hands' splices is well-fitted by the Wilson model (M. N. Wilson, Superconducting Magnets. Oxford, U.K.: Clarendon, 1983, p. 314.), i.e. the splice resistance is inversely proportional to the splice length;
2. The soldering is crucial to have resistance of the order of nano ohms, otherwise the resistance increases by at least two orders of magnitude;
3. The resistance in the 'praying hands' configuration is of the order of a few nano-ohm, while the 'shaking hands' is even lower.

Figure 6: Test setup of the rope splice: three “praying hands” and two “shaking hands” configurations.

The final production of the cable has been launched (14 spools of 100 meters of rope), and the delivery to CIEMAT (Madrid, Spain) is foreseen for November 2023.

3.2.2 Formers

The careful selection of materials for the magnet, particularly the formers, is of paramount importance due to the high ramp rate. Optimal performance demands minimal conductivity in the formers to prevent eddy currents that could distort the magnetic field, introduce time delays relative to the ramped magnet current, and generate excess heat in the coils.

Equally critical is the machinability of the chosen material and the determination of the minimum rib thickness between adjacent grooves. This thickness significantly influences the magnet transfer function, affecting the current (or number of conductors) required to achieve a specific magnetic field.

Aluminium-bronze has been selected as material for the former for its low electrical conductivity, ready availability as raw material, and favourable manufacturing properties.

Figure 7: Test former made at CERN, and retouched by an external company.

To gain valuable insights into the material and establish the minimum feasible wall thickness, a straight former was successfully manufactured at the CERN workshop (see Fig. 7). Employing rounded tools during machining eliminated sharp corners at the groove bottoms, resulting in a slight reduction in minimum rib thickness. This approach not only enhanced mechanical stability but also mitigated stress accumulation points and reduced the void volume to be filled by impregnation.

The experiment revealed minimum rib thicknesses ranging from 1.24 to 0.74 mm in 0.1 mm increments, all of which demonstrated remarkable mechanical stability. Based on the cumulative experience from various projects, a minimum rib thickness of 0.4 mm is deemed acceptable for this aluminium-bronze material.

In essence, the successful construction of the former in aluminium-bronze attests to its suitability, underlining its construction readiness for demanding applications in magnet systems.

3.2.3 Envelope tube

The envelope tube is the outermost of the 3 coaxial tubes constituting the winding (Fig. 8). It has multiple purposes: (1) mechanical support to counteract the Lorentz forces, and (2) serving as a container for wax and a vacuum/pressure vessel during wax impregnation. It is made of the same material (aluminium-bronze) as the formers in order to not introduce thermal contraction differences. It has two circular grooves at its ends for mounting and sealing the wax impregnation tools.

Figure 8: Envelope tube

3.2.4 End plates

The magnet is closed at its two ends by two end plates (Fig. 9), made of glass-fiber composite. These end plates lock the 3 tubes axially. They have 4 protrusions (1) on their external sides to azimuthally position the magnet in an external support structure. The disk at the current lead/splice box end of the magnet (not visible in the figure) has similar protrusions on its inner side, to lock the 3 tubes azimuthally. This alignment concept allows differential thermal contraction in the radial direction.

The bottom plate has a G1/4 tapped hole (2) for a hose adapter, serving as wax inlet during impregnation. The top plate has two slots to allow the 2x7 cables enter the splice box. Both plates are fixed to the inner former by bolts (4) and the one at the layer-jump end is also sealed to it by rubber O-rings (not visible here but illustrated in Fig. 9) for the wax impregnation. This O-ring remains in the magnet and plays no further role after impregnation.

Figure 9: End plates. Left: bottom of the magnet (during impregnation). Right: top of the magnet (during impregnation).

3.2.5 Splice box

In order to avoid openings on the cylindrical walls of the magnet (which makes the sealing for the 5-bar impregnation much easier), the conductors are guided out from the formers axially, and the “shaking hands” splices are embedded in a “splice box” attached to the end of the magnet, as shown in Fig. 10. The splice box (1) and its cover (4) are made from G10. The cables enter the box through the openings (2) and join the cables of the other layer on both sides of the aperture. Separate slots (3) are implemented for each splice to position and insulate them. The two lead cables exit the cover (4) through the slots (5), which at the same time serve as outlets for wax during impregnation. The splice box is going to be impregnated together with the magnet in the same process. The covers (6) are installed after the impregnation to cover the outlets (5).

Figure 10: Splice box.

3.3 LIST OF PROCEDURES

3.3.1 Winding

To accumulate proficiency in winding this specific configuration, a first test with 2×8 twisted ropes, each composed of 7 copper dummy strands insulated by a polyester braid, were wound onto the straight aluminum-bronze former as illustrated in Section 2.2.2 (refer to Fig. 11). It is noteworthy that the copper strands used in this phase were considerably less rigid compared to the final NbTi strands. Winding on the straight former was a relatively straightforward process with no notable challenges.

The polyester braid exhibited stability and remained securely in place along the ropes. However, the braid pattern (Fig. 11) was found to be loose and provided insufficient coverage. This resulted in metallic surfaces being visible through the braid (visible in Fig. 11), leading to shorting of all ropes to the formers after a few turns. For the final magnet, a more compact and robust braid pattern is essential.

Additionally, an important observation was made regarding the sharp outer edges of the grooves, which had the potential to easily damage the insulation of the ropes during winding. It is imperative that these edges be rounded during the manufacturing process to prevent such damage.

The test former was retouched by the company Smartsol Engineering (Fig. 11):

- Add chamfers to the outer edges of the groove to avoid the damage of the rope insulation during winding. Fillets would be preferable, but it was considered being very difficult to implement in a

retouching procedure, where the workpiece is mounted to a different machine, and needs to be aligned very precisely. It can nevertheless be implemented during manufacturing, without removing the former from the CNC machine between the milling of the grooves and the fillets.

– Add M6 tapped holes between each turn at the top and the bottom where the wall has the largest thickness. These would allow to install temporary clamps during winding to fix the ropes within the groove.

A second winding test was carried out with the retouched former using the superconducting ropes (6 NbTi strands around a central copper strand). The superconducting strands are much stiffer than the dummy copper rope, but the winding could be made using the same custom tools to guide the ropes from the spools to the former. The rounded edges of the groove do not damage the insulation, so this feature will be kept in future formers. The foreseen temporary clamps (Fig. 11) are now essential not only to keep the ropes in the groove, but also to provide some tension during the winding. The ropes are placed into the groove, then the clamps are placed with a light pressure on the ropes, the winding tension is increased and finally the clamps are tightened. There is an intermediate rubber piece to protect the ropes from the aluminium clamps. However, most of the ropes were in direct electrical contact with the former, likely due to the voids appearing in between the polyester filaments when the ropes are bent into the grooves. It was decided to increase the filling factor of the polyester braid up to 99% to solve this problem.

Figure 11. Aluminium clamps to hold the superconducting ropes inside the grooves.

A third winding test was foreseen with the reinforced insulation. However, the outer diameter of the new insulated ropes increased up to 3.15 mm. It was not possible to insert them into the grooves. It was decided to make a simplified winding test by machining wider grooves with similar bending radius in a plate (Fig. 12). The insulation test was performed successfully. All the ropes were able to withstand 500 V with insulating resistance above 1 G Ω , being the bottom rope the one performing the minimum values. A last insulation test was performed at 1 kV on the bottom rope featuring a resistance of 970 M Ω . These resistance values are considered satisfactory because the ropes are not impregnated yet.

Figure: 12. Superconducting ropes with denser polyester braided insulation were placed inside wider grooves.

No further winding tests are foreseen. The same techniques and tooling used for the tests will be used for the winding of the superconducting ropes in the real size formers. The groove of the definitive formers will have 6.5 mm width and 22.3 mm depth to allocate 2 times 7 ropes with 99% filling factor

polyester braided insulation. There will be a layer jump to avoid intermediate splices, using some ancillary pieces to guide the ropes (Figs. 1 and 2). In consequence, the impregnation will be performed in a single pass for the entire magnet, once both formers are completely wound. Glass fiber tapes will be wrapped around each former to ease the wax flow. An additional polyimide sheet will enhance the electrical insulation between both formers and the outer envelope tube.

3.3.2 Impregnation

Superconducting coils impregnated with epoxy resins typically require multiple quenches before reaching their nominal current levels, displaying a training behavior. However, recent examination of a short Nb₃Sn cable [5] suggests that wax may offer a more effective alternative to epoxy, especially in stress-managed coils with external mechanical support, as demonstrated in a test where a short Nb₃Sn cable impregnated with wax reached the short-sample limit without any quenches.

The aluminium-bronze test former, wound with 2x7 ropes, was impregnated with wax in an extremely simple setup (using a kapton sheet around it as a vacuum envelope, sealed with self-adhesive kapton tape), following the method developed for the SuShi septum project [6]. This method was meticulously designed to avoid the formation of voids within the wax volume during the freeze-out phase, where wax contracts by about 15%. Interestingly, even in the absence of overpressure in the simple setup during freeze-out, the wound structure exhibited remarkable stability, requiring significant force to remove the ropes from their grooves.

The presence of the polyester braid emerged as a crucial element in this process, functioning as a retainer of wax to prevent the formation of significant voids in the event of a failure during the refill process during freeze-out.

The setup for impregnation is shown in Fig.13. The magnet itself serves as the impregnation mold, no external vacuum system is required. Wax is injected into the magnet from the bottom [not shown here, see Fig. 9, feature (2)], and fills first the magnet, then the splice box, and finally a local reservoir mounted directly to the top of the magnet surrounding the entire splice box, which consist of several parts: the bottom and top plates, the cylindrical wall and a central shaft (1). The different parts of the reservoir are sealed to each other and to the magnet by rubber O-rings (2). Wax exits the splice box and fills the reservoir through the slots (3) where the two current lead cables of the magnet exit the splice box. Injection of wax is made under vacuum which is provided via the connector (4) at the top of the reservoir. A transparent hose (5) is mounted to the side of the reservoir to monitor the level of wax. Note that wax below the level of the exit slots from the magnet (3) cannot enter the magnet, and wax level needs to be maintained above this at all times until the end of the impregnation process. Once the reservoir is full, the valve at the inlet (not shown) is closed, the vacuum pump is detached from the connector (4) and is replaced by a pressurized air or nitrogen hose to provide 5 bar. Cooling of the magnet will start from the bottom and inside the bore, and will progress upwards as described in [6] to guarantee a constantly progressing solid-liquid interface. In order to avoid a sealed feedthrough for the two cables (6+1 twisted cable in a polyester braid), which would be very difficult to realize, the cables would be coiled up within the reservoir, either at the top (using some simple support) to avoid being submerged in wax (the reservoir not being fully filled), or “where they happen to be”. In the latter case the cables would need some cleaning (ether can be used) for their end section where they would be spliced to the power leads. The inner and the outer walls of the reservoir are made slightly conical to make their removal from the remaining, solid wax easier. The remaining wax needs to be mechanically removed from around the splice box as the last step.

Figure 13: Wax impregnation mold.

3.3.3 Assembly

Assembly procedure:

- 1) Install the former on the winding machine;
- 2) Start the winding of 2x7 ropes on the inner former, making regular high-voltage tests, as described in subsection 2.3;
- 3) Cover the contour of the footprint of the layer jump clamps on the outer surface of the inner former by self-adhesive kapton tape. Install the layer jump clamps (Fig. 1)
- 4) Install the insulation surface between formers, composed of two layers strips of glass fiber tape + two layers one strip/sheet of polyimide (kapton), at the end high-voltage test to verify the insulation;

- 5) Insert the outer former;
- 6) Start the winding of 2x7 ropes on the second layer;
- 7) Finish the winding, cover with an external insulation surface as point 4;
- 8) Install the external envelope tube (Fig. 8);
- 9) Mount the two end plates (Fig. 9);
- 10) Mount the splice box (Fig. 10);
- 11) Make the 13 joints of the ropes;
- 12) Realize the voltage taps useful for the quench detection and monitoring;
- 13) Implement the wax-impregnation, as described in section 3.3.2;
- 14) Remove of the reservoir and clean the splice box of the excess wax.

4. Readiness Table

The section shows the table of readiness of the main components and procedures described in the previous sections, highlighting the status in two levels: ready (no constraint for the final production), and medium (additional investigations to be done). Moreover, comments are added to justify the status.

Components	Readiness status	Comments
Conductor	ready	Final production launched
Formers	ready	Company for the final production to be found
Envelope tube	medium	Missing mechanical simulation for establishing the final thickness
End plates	ready	
Splice box	medium	To verify the production by CNC-machining and material (G10)
Procedures		
Winding	ready	Winding techniques ready, 3D model ready, fabrication drawings ongoing
Impregnation	ready	Design ready, components to be manufactured with the other parts.
Assembly	medium	To be defined the interlayer and the external surfaces of the formers.

5. Conclusion

The report highlights the construction readiness of a combined CCT demonstrator, detailing key components and procedures.

The conductor is fully characterized and ready for production. Aluminum-bronze formers and glass-fiber reinforced PEEK end plates are the chosen materials.

The importance of winding tests, wax impregnation, and assembly procedures is emphasized, with a focus on improving superconducting ropes.

The document underscores the effectiveness of wax impregnation in preventing quenches and the significance of a polyester braid in the process.

The readiness table provides a comprehensive status update on various components and procedures, allowing for a well-informed approach to the project.

The next step is to launch the production of all the components for the final assembly at CIEMAT (beneficiary responsible for construction Task 8.4), and to verify the integration of the demonstrator with the test facility (FREIA, Uppsala, Sweden)[7] which is in charge for the cold test.

6. References

- [1] European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, (2021) Grant Agreement Number 101004730 - I.FAST.
- [2] De Matteis, E., Ceruti, G., Mariotto, S., Prioli, M., & Sorti, S. (2022). Conceptual Design of combined CCT in LTS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389851>
- [3] Alessandria, F., Angius, S., Bellomo, G., Fabbriatore, P., Farinon, S., Gambardella, U., Marabotto, R., Musenich, R., Repetto, R., Sorbi, M., Volpini, G. (2009) Technical design report of a superconducting model dipole for FAIR SIS300, *INFN/code-08/001* <https://air.unimi.it/handle/2434/72640>
- [4] De Matteis, E., & I.FAST WP8 members. (2022) Characterization of the first length of superconductor for low losses, *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5901601>
- [5] M. Daly, B. Auchmann, A. Brem, C. Hug, S. Sidorov, S. Otten, M. Dhallé, Z. Guo, A. Kario, and H. T. Kate, “Improved training in paraffin-wax impregnated Nb₃Sn Rutherford cables demonstrated in BOX samples,” *Superconductor Science and Technology*, vol. 35, no. 5, p. 055014, Apr. 2022, publisher: IOP Publishing. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6668/ac6123>
- [6] D. Barna, K. Brunner, J Borburgh, M. Atanasov, F. Lackner, O. Maja, K. Pepitone, R. Santiago Kern, C. Svanberg, T. Bagni, “Test results of the first wax-impregnated, Nb-Ti canted cosine theta septum magnet ‘SuShi’”, *Proceedings of MT28, Aix-en-Provence, France*; to appear in *IEEE Transactions in Applied Superconductivity*.
- [7] R. Ruber et al., “Accelerator development at the FREIA Laboratory,” *Journal of Instrumentation*, 2021, 16.07: P07039.